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Hospitality in the light of Indian culture and Sanskrit Sahitya

Dr. Hemant Sharma¹

Indian culture and Sanskrit literature have been guiding the society since ancient times. This culture has been known for its glorious glory and sublime form since time immemorial. This culture has always proclaimed the wish for Humanity. Ethics, knowledge-science, policy and religion etc. contained in it have always been instructing the best path for the welfare of the world. Indian culture has been full of excellent human values, सर्वे भवन्तु सुखिनः have been its basic mantra. It is the only culture in the world which sees the whole world as one family. For the smooth functioning of the social system, Indian culture divided human society into four ashrams. This Chaturashrami(चतुराश्रमी) system of Indian culture is practical as well as very scientific. Indian culture arranged Brahmacharya Ashram (ब्रह्मचर्य आश्रम) for education, to become proficient in art and scientific knowledge. While living righteously, for his family growth through progeny and for prescribing various social functions, that called Grihastha Ashram(गृहस्थ आश्रम). Vanprastha ashram(वानप्रस्थ आश्रम) was for self-retirement of Papadi Dosha(पापादिदोष), attainment of supreme purushartha, salvation and for leading a life of austerity. Sanyas Ashram(सन्यास आश्रम) was for self-welfare by abstaining from all worldly subjects. in this Chaturashrami system, Grihasthashram was considered to be the best.

यथा वायुं समाश्रित्य वर्तन्ते सर्वजन्तवः ।

तथा गृहस्थमाश्रित्य वर्तन्ते सर्व आश्रमाः ॥ (Manusmriti- 3.77)

सर्वेषामपि चैतेषां वेदस्मृतिविधानतः ।

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गृहस्थ उच्यते श्रेष्ठः स लीनेतान्बिभर्ति हि ॥ (Manusmriti - 6.89)

In our culture, hospitality was given very prominent position & it was even called a Yajna.(यज्ञ) Yajna was obligatory duty for every human being. For the smooth operation of the social system, physical and spiritual progress, welfare of the living beings, the five Mahayagyas were rendered for every householder. which hospitality was also called Yagya-

अध्यापनं ब्रह्मयज्ञः पितृयज्ञस्तु तर्पणम् ।

हौमो देवो बलिर्भूतो नृयज्ञोऽतिथिपूजनम् ॥ (Manusmriti - 3.70)

Manu called eternal self-study as Brahma yajna(ब्रह्मयज्ञ), tarpan for the gods as Pitri yajna(पितृयज्ञ), Devhomadi as dev yajna(देवयज्ञ), Balivaishvadeva(बलिवैश्वदेव) as bhutyajna(भूतयज्ञ). and Nriyagya(नृयज्ञ) is guest worship. The question arising Who is the guest? ‘अनित्यास्य स्थिति र्यस्मात्तस्मादतिथिरुच्यते’ (Vachaspatyam) i.e. the one whose date of arrival is not fixed is called a ‘guest’. But this is just a general definition of a guest. About the guest, its symptoms were discussed in detail in the Dharmshastra and Smritigranthas. Defining the characteristics of a guest in Apastamba Dharmasutra, a Brahmin who is master in Vedas, possesses the characteristics of srotyadi(श्रोत्यादि), practices self-righteousness and visits the householder for only religious purpose is guest. - वधर्मयुक्तं कुटुम्बिनमभ्यागच्छति धर्मपुरस्कारो नाऽन्यप्रयोजनः सोऽतिथिर्भवति । (Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.5)

In the Gautam Dharmasutra, the character of a guest is that the people living in another village, staying for only one night and comes in the midday or evening time are called “Guest”. असमानग्रामोऽतिथिरैकरात् रिकाऽधिवृक्षसूर्योपस्थायी । (Gautam Dharmasutra - 1.5.36)

Manusmritikar has called a shrautriya brahminisht brahmin, who stays for one night, whose date of arrival and stay is not fixed is called Atithi-

एकरात्रं तु निवसन्नतिथिर्ब्राह्मणः स्मृतः ।

अनित्यं हि स्थितो यस्मात्तस्मादतिथिरुच्यते ॥ (Manusmriti - 3.102)

Yajnavalkya writes in relation to the guest that the Shrotriya Vedapathi on the way traveller is Atithi. every virtuous householder who wishes to attain Brahmaloaka, should provide hospitality to those kind of travellers -

अध्वनीनोऽतिथिर्ज्ञेयः श्रोत्रियो वेदपारगः ।

मान्यावेतौ गृहस्थस्य ब्रह्मलोकमभीप्सितः ॥ (Yajnavalkyasmriti - P 54)

Thus it is clear that in the ancient tradition only the ascetic Vedic scholar Shrotriya Brahmins were often called Atithi. Taittiriya Upanishad writes 'अतिथि देवो भव' (taittiriyopnishad- 1.11) for such guests only. in the Shankh Smriti 'For a man who assumes the duties & responsibilities of a householder, the guest is Acharya for him.

यथा भर्ता प्रभुः स्त्रीणां वर्णानां ब्राह्मणो यथा ।

अतिथिस्तद्देवास्य गृहस्थस्य प्रभुः स्मृतः ॥ (Shankh Smriti 5.7)

In Chanakyaniti, austere guests are called 'सर्वस्याभ्यागतो गुरुः' (Chanakyaniti - 5.1)

This type of guest deserves to be the guru of all. Much glory has been sung in the scriptures for the hospitality of such a guest. धन्यं यशस्यमायुष्यं स्वर्ग्यं वाऽतिथिपूजनम् । (Manusmriti - 3.106)

In the Apastamba Dharmasutra it is said that by hospitality, a person frees from all troubles and attains the fruits of heaven- तस्य पूजायां शान्तिः स्वर्गश्च । (Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.6)

It has been said in the *Shankh Smriti* that the benetits which a householder gets from the yajnadi, obtains more benefits in very short period of time by giving hospitality to Atithi.

न यज्ञैर्दक्षिणाभिश्च वह्निशुश्रूषया न च ।

गृहीस्वर्गमवाप्नोति यथा चातिथिपूजनात् ॥ (Shankh Smriti 5.13)

The Apastamba Dharmashastra discusses about Atithi hospitality in detail. it has been said that a guest stays for one night, the family members are entitled for pleasure what a man can get on this earth. By staying for two nights, he conquers the worlds of space. One who stays for three nights attains the heavenly worlds. One who stays till the fourth night attains infinite bliss and the one who stays for many nights attains infinite happiness.

एकरात्रं चेदतिथिन्वासयेत्पार्थिवल्लोकानभिजयति द्वितीययाऽऽन्तरिक्ष्यांस्तृतीयया दिव्यांश्चतुर्थ्या परावतो लोकानपरिमिताभिपरिमिताल्लोकानभिजयतीति विज्ञायते । (Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.16)

It is clear that a person with the above-mentioned characteristics is called a guest, but in the society we see that one who does not have the above qualifications of a guest is also called a guest, for solution of its in Indian theology has said in the Chaturvarnya system that the person who have even not fulfil above mentioned symptoms, but everyone should be respected by guest religion. In this way people of all castes and religion were accepted as guests. It is said in the

scriptures irrespective of the caste and religion of the guest, on receipt of him, he should be well received with guest religion. As it is said in the Paraskara Grihyasutra-

पादौ प्रक्षाल्याचम्य अतिथिप्राप्तौ पादप्रक्षालनपूर्वकं गन्धमाल्यादिभिरभ्यर्च्य अन्नं परिवेष्य हन्त तेऽन्नमिदं मनुष्याय इति संकल्प्य तमाशयेत् । (Parasargrhyasutra P 138)

It has been said in *Manusmriti* that as soon as a guest is received, he should be treated with due respect.

संप्राप्ताय त्वतिथये प्रदद्यादासनोदके ।

अन्नं चैव यथाशक्ति सत्कृत्य विधिपूर्वकम् ॥ (Manusmriti - 3.99)

Jajnavalkya said if guests of all the varnas are received together, their rites should be completed according to their varna order. if any guest comes in the evening, he should also be given proper hospitality.

अतिथित्वेन वर्णानां देयं शक्त्यानुपूर्वशः ।

अप्रणोद्योऽतिथिः सायमपि वाग्भृत्णोदकैः ॥

(Jajnavalkyasmriti - Acharyaadhyaya P 53)

Manu has also envisaged arrangements according to their categories of the guests

आसनावसथौ शय्यामनुब्रज्यामुपासनाम् ।

उत्तमेषूत्तमं कुर्याद्हीने हीनं समे समम् ॥ (Manusmriti - 3.107)

At present, this system of Manu can be seen literally in our society and is also very relevant. Whether it is the government or the community, care of the guests, service and hospitality, etc. are arranged according to the upper middle and lowest order. In the government also, there is a different type of arrangement for the reception of high officials, different for middle class officers and different for lower class employees. A similar description is also found in Gautam Dharmasutra, where the method of hospitality has been described according to eligibility. Hospitality of Shrotriya guest should be done with padhya(पाद्य) arghya(अर्घ्य) and food etc. Hospitality of illiterate but a virtuous guest with medium grade food and Hospitality of virtuous but educated guest with grass, water, place and welcome words.

श्रीत्रियस्य तु पाद्यार्घ्यमन्नविशेषांश्च प्रकारयेत् ।

मध्यतोऽन्नदानमवैद्ये साधुवृत्ते ।

विपरीतेषु तृणोदकभूमिस्वागतमन्ततः पूजाऽनत्याशश्च ।

(Gautam Dharmasutra - 1.5.30-32-33)

It has been said in Apastambadharmasutra that on receipt of the guest, speak cordially with him and satisfy him with various good substances, milk etc. and if not possible than welcomed at least with water. सान्त्वयित्वा तर्पयेद्द्रव्यैर्भक्ष्यैरद्विरवराध्यनेति । (Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.14)

In the scriptures, it has been told to attain heaven by the hospitality of both dear and unpleasant guests.

प्रियाः अप्रियाश्चाऽतिथितयः स्वर्गं लोकं गमयन्तीति विज्ञायते ।

(Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.5)

It is said in Apastambadharmasutra that if a guest comes near the king, then the king should also worship the guest more than himself. राजानं चेदतिथिरभ्यागच्छेच्छ्रेयसीमस्मै पूजामात्मनः कारयेत् । (Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.11)

It was said in the scriptures, while specifying the guests through deep contemplation and rumination, food of hostile person should not be eaten by the guest. द्विषन्दिषतो वा नान्नमश्रयाद्दोषेण वा मीमांसमानस्य मीमांसितस्य वा । (Aapastamba Dharmasutra - 2.3.19)

After treating the guest well, he should be taken to the border of the village.

अतिथिं श्रोत्रियं तृप्तमासीमान्तमनुव्रजेत् ।

अहःशेषं सहासीत् शिष्टैरिष्टैश्च बन्धुभिः ॥ (Yajnavalkyasmriti - P 55)

Indian sages have said about hospitality that the householder (गृहस्थ) should do hospitality with the best things. if someone is incapable then he can do hospitality in the normal things. In the absence of anything, treat the guest by giving grass, land, water and sweet voice-

तृणानि भूमिरुदकं वाक्चतुर्थी च सुनृता ।

एतान्यपि सतां गेहे नोच्छिद्यन्ते कदाचन (Manusmriti - 3.101)

in Indian culture women's power has always given priority. while expressing their generosity towards women power, the scriptures said if the newly married, virgin (कुमारी) and pregnant woman are present, they should satisfy without any thought before the guests -

सुवासिनीः कुमारीश्च रोगिणो गर्भिणीः स्त्रियः ।

अतिथिभ्योऽग्र एवैतान्भोजयेद्विचारयन् ॥ (Manusmriti - 3.114)

Indian culture was so liberal and practical that created rules and principles according to everyone, from special people to common people. Sublime evidence of this generosity of Indian culture and glorious hospitality tradition is widely found in the Laukik Sanskrit

literature as well. The great poets like Bhas, Kalidas, Bhavabhuti etc. have made a very beautiful and idealistic representation of the discharge of Nryajna in Indian hospitality tradition. Whether the householder, whether the Vanprasthi, whether the sannyasi used to follow all the hospitality religion with full devotion and dedication. People used to give hospitality not only to the acquaintances but also to the strangers with full devotion. in Buddhist culture looking at the guest religion, Acharya Ramji Upadhyay has said in his book Prachin Bhartiya Sahitya ki Sanskritik Bhoomika that 'In this era at least some householders in every town and village were famous for hospitality. Small and big monks used to reach their door without any hindrance. If there was a great Mahatma, he was given a high level hospitality (Upadhyay 261). Many such examples are found in the Laukik Sanskrit literature from which it is known that at that time the guests were treated like household members. in the first Chapter of Bhasa's Swapnavasavadattana, When Padmavati enters the ashram the Tapsees present there welcoming Padmavati say that Tapovan is the guest's own home-

तापसी- चिरं जीव । प्रविश जाते ! प्रविश । तपोवनानि नामाऽतिथिजनस्य स्वकगेहम् ।
पद्मावती- भवतु आर्ये ! विश्वस्तास्मि । अनेन बहुमानवचनेन अनुगृहीतास्मि ।

(*Svapnavasavadattam* 20)

It is known from Pt. Ambikadatta Vyasa's composition *Shivrajvijay* even when India wasn't independent, people followed the hospitality tradition with full spirit and devotion. When Yogiraj awakened from Samadhi and reached the nearest Gurukul, there the sublime nature of their prompt hospitality can be seen-

अहो प्रबुद्धो मुनिः ! प्रबुद्धो मुनिः । इत एवाऽऽगच्छति, इत एवाऽऽगच्छति, सत्कार्योऽयं
सत्कार्योऽयम् इति तौ सम्भ्रान्ती बभुवतुः । (*Sivrajvijayam* 20)

In Indian culture, hospitality has been given such a wide glory. Even the Dev community doesn't shy away from it. In the *Harshacharita* composed by the great poet Banabhatta, Saraswati and Savitri extend the exile hospitality to Dadhichi and Vikukshi-

दूरादेव च तुरगादवततार निवारितपरिजनश्च तेन द्वितीयेन साधुना सह चरणाभ्यामेव
सविनयमुपसर्ष । कृतोपसंग्रणौ तौ साविली समं सरस्वत्या किसलयसनदानादिना सुकुसुम
फलाख्यावसानेन वनवासोचितेनातिथ्येन यथाक्रममुपजग्राह । (*Harshacharitam* 52)

In *Abhijnanshakuntalam* composed by Kalidasa, Anasuya asks dear friend Shakuntala to bring fruits, arghya, water for hospitality-

अनसूया- इदानीमतिथिविशेषलाभेन । हला शकन्तले गच्छोदजम् । फल मिश्रमर्च्यमुपहर ।
इदं पादोदकं भविष्यति । (Abhijnananshakuntalam 50)

In ancient times the guests were also pleased with the hospitality and expressed themselves. Dushyant tells Anasuya that my hospitality was done only by the sweet voice of yours-

राजा- भवतीनां सुनृतयैव गिरा कृतमातिथ्यम् । (Abhijnananshakuntalam 50)

India also had a distinctive style of asking for the introduction of the guests. In Indian culture genre of asking the guests for introduction is amazing. Of the huge heart sensation Indian culture, its wide generosity, its purified principles, its universal brotherhood and virtuousness etc. can be gauged from its pure and soulful hospitality style. In which style introduction of the guest was asked anyone can be glad listen that. The intimacy and respect that was shown in the introduction can only be done by Indian culture. You can see how sublime the ancient Indian hospitality style is, How elegant is the manner of asking, The person asking the question is saying that there is a desire to ask something after hearing your sweet and melodious voice and seeing the gravely soft figure. Look at the melody of the questions - Arya! What are those characters who became blessed to be associated with you? O Arya! Which country did you make unhappy with your separation? Which lineage do you embellish? Why did you give so much pain to your soft body? and so on and so forth . The philosophy of this sublime style is found everywhere in Sanskrit literature.

in *Harshacharitam* The etiquette and decency with which Saraswati and Savitri are asking the introduction of the guests who have come to at the doors undoubtedly commendable and exemplary for everyone, this behaviour of their love towards the guests is amazing.

तत्कथयागमनेनापुण्यभाक् कतमो देशो विजृम्भितविरहव्यथः शून्यतां नीतः ? क्व वा गन्तव्यं?
को वायमपहृतहरहृङ्कारराहङ्कारोऽपर इवानन्वजो युवा ? किन्नामो वा समृद्धतपसः पितुरयम्
अमृतवर्षिणी कौस्तुभमणिरिव हरेर्हृदयमाह्लादयति ? का वास्य त्रिभुवननमस्याप्रभातसन्ध्यामेव
महत्स्तेजसो जननी ? कानि वास्य पुण्यभाञ्जि भजन्त्यभिख्यामक्षराणि ? आर्यं परिज्ञानेऽप्ययमेव
कौतुकानुरोधिनो हृदयस्येति । (Harshacharitam 53-54)

This sublime and serene style of curiosity about guest introduction can also be seen in the play *Abhijnanshakuntalanam* composed by the great poet Kalidas.

प्रियंवदा- (जनान्तिकम्) अनसूये को नु खल्वेष चतुरगम्भीराकृतिर्मधुर इव प्रियमालपन् प्रभाववानिव लक्ष्यते ।

अनसूया- सखि, ममाप्यस्ति कौतूहलम् । पृच्छामि तावदेनम् । (प्रकाशं) आर्यस्य मधुरालापोजनितो विश्रम्भो मां मन्त्रयते – कतम आर्येण राजर्षिवंशोऽलंक्रियते । कतमो वा विरहपर्युत्सुकजन कृतो देश । किं निमित्तं वा सुकुमारतरोऽपि तपोवनगमनपरिश्रमस्यात्मा पदमुपनीत । (*Abhijnananshakuntalam* 51)

It is proved from the above hospitality style that same tradition of hospitality used to familiar & unfamiliar guests. The hospitality of the guest who came to the house was the obligatory duty of everyone. Along with the general public, the king was also ready to welcome the guests. On the arrival of Vasubhuti in *Ratnavali* drama, the king himself goes ahead for hospitality and says-

वसुभूति- (उपसृत्य) जयतु देवः ।

राजा- (उत्थाय) आर्यः अभिवादये ।

वसुभूति- आयुष्मान् भव !

राजा- आसनमासनमार्याय । (*Ratnavali Natika* - 4.13, p. 154)

Similarly, in *Karpoormanjari*, King Chandrapal himself offers hospitality to Kaulacharya Bhairavnand- राजा- इदमासनम्, उपविशतु भैरवानन्दः । (*Karpoormanjari* -1.24, P. 44)

Ram-Lakshman and Vishwamitra are duly and warmly welcomed in the Janaksabha in *Ramayanachampu*- “तत्र विधिवदभ्यर्चितः कथितदशरथतनयवृत्तान्तः कौशिकः” (Shastri 100)

In the *Uttararamcharitam* of Mahakavi Bhavabhutikrit, Ram welcomes Ashtavakra with humility and says:

रामः- भगवन् ! अभिवादये । इत आस्यताम् । (*Uttararamcharitam* - P 18)

In this play *Vanadevata* provides hospitality to Taapsee with forest manner-

(नेपथ्ये)

स्वागतं तपोधनायाः ।

वनदेवता- (अर्घ्यं विकीर्य)

यथेच्छाभोग्यं वो वनमिदमयं मे सुदिवसः

सतां सद्भिः सङ्गः कथमपि हि पुण्येन भवति ।

तरुच्छायां तोयं यदपि तपसां योग्यशमनं

फलं वा मूलं वा तदपि न पराधीनमिह वः ॥ (*Uttararamcharitam* - P 82-83)

In the *Shishupalavadham* epic composed by Magha, to the hospitality of Narada Muni, Dwarkadhish Shri Krishna rises from his seat and establishes him on the highest seat-

तमर्घ्यमर्घादिकयाऽऽदिपूरुषः सपर्यया साधु स पर्यपूजत् ।
 गृहानुपैतुं प्रणयादभीप्सवो भवन्ति नापुण्यकृतां मनीषिणः ॥
 न यावदेतावुदपश्यदुत्थितौ जनस्तुषाराञ्जनपर्वताकृती ।
 स्वहस्तदत्ते मुनिमासने मुनिश्चिरन्तनस्तावदमिन्यवीविशत् ॥

(*Shishupalvadham* - 1.14-15)

The Arsh form of Indian hospitality is reflected in the drama *Kundamala*. In the play when Ram enters the tapovan to search Sita in that time Maharishi Valmiki know that Ram has come to this tapovan, he follows the hospitality tradition and asks Kanva to show beauty of tapovan very nicely and amusment of Ram-

कण्वः- आदिष्टोऽस्मि भगवता वाल्मीकिना- कण्व कण्व दाशरथिं नैमिषारण्यरामणीयकदर्शनेन
 विनोदय इति । (*Kundmala*- 4.1 P. 95)

In the Raghuvansh epic composed by Kalidasa, when Dilip leaves for Vasisthashram, the Brahmins of the villages on the way give him hospitality through Padyadi(पाद्यादि) and in Vasistha's ashram hospitality given by the the sages with Arsha tradition-

ग्रामेष्वात्मविसृष्टेषु यूपचिह्नेषु यज्वनाम् ।
 अमोघाः प्रतिगृह्णन्तावर्च्यानुपदमाशिषः ॥
 तस्मै सभ्याः सभार्याय गोप्त्रे गुप्तमतेन्द्रियाः ।
 अर्हणामर्हते चक्रुर्मुनयो नयचक्षुषे ॥ (*Raghuvansh* - 1.44, 55)

It is known from the *Mrcchakatika* composed by Shudraka, women who made a living by prostitution followed religion of hospitality. On the arrival of the clown Madhavaya, Vasantasena welcomes him and says-

विदूषक- स्वस्ति भवत्यै ।

वसन्तसेना- अये मैतेय ! (उत्थाय) स्वागतम् । इदमासनम्, अत्रोपविश्यताम् ।
 (*Mricchakatika* - P 325)

In the *Dharmshastras* and *Smritigranthas*, priority was given to Grihalakshmi for hospitality. The women of the family were entrusted with the hospitality of the guests coming from faraway. Hospitality was considered the main duty of women.

“अपत्यस्य जननं जातस्य परिपालनं प्रतिदिनं चातिथिमित्रभोजनादेलोकव्यवहारस्य प्रत्यक्षं
 भार्यैव निदानम्” (*Manusmriti* - 9.27, Vritti, P. 462)

In Sanskrit literature, holy character of women discharging guest religion is narrating the glory of Indian culture. It is known from the play *Abhijnanshakuntalam* composed by Kalidas. Shakuntala has

the responsibility of hospitality in the play, when Vaikhanas requests to Dushyant to receive hospitality, then Dushyant ask whether Maharishi Kanva is in the ashram or not? Then Vaikhanas says that he has left this hospitality work on his Duhita Shakuntala-

वैखानस- “इदानीमेव दुहितरं शकुन्तलामतिथिसत्काराय नियुज्य दैवमस्या प्रतिकूलं शमयितुं सोमतीर्थं गतः” (Abhijnananshakuntalam - P.25-27)

Thus innumerable examples of guest religion and Hospitality are filled in various Indian scriptures and poetry.

Conclusion

Hospitality was foremost in the sublime tradition of Indian culture. This country has always given priority to hospitality. from the Vedic Era till the modern period People have been discharging hospitality. In ancient times, on the one way the householders ready to discharge hospitality with full dedication and devotion, and on the other way the guests were also ready to cooperate by following their Atithidharma. the tradition of hospitality in the society was driven by the mutual loyalty of both. The sublime form of hospitality which is visible to us in ancient Indian culture, is seen in a changed form today. Although people are discharging hospitality religion in the society with some changes in modern times, but the enthusiasm, happy and love which were there in ancient times have decreased. Earlier the date of arrival of the guest was not fixed, but in modern times there will be few places where the date is not fixed. In the era of modern hurry, in the era of inflation-unemployment-unreliability, although the nature of hospitality has changed, but even today, enlightened and aware people are ready for hospitality with full dedication and enthusiasm. due to this generous and sublime hospitality tradition, India is also establishing its highest position on the world map.

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